

Criteria of relevance and appropriateness.

Category	ID	Criteria	Aspect	
Clarity	RC1	The document focuses its research theme on Social Debt (SD) in agile software development teams.	Thematic axis of the research.	
	RC2	The study presents the causes and/or effects, and/or metrics, and/or patterns, and/or tools, and/or domains that enable the identification of social debt in agile software development teams.	Causes, effects, and metrics to determine Social Debt (SD).	
Rigor	RC3	Are the objectives of the study explicitly and/or clearly defined?	Study Objectives.	
	RC4	Is the research methodology and the procedures used appropriate, clearly detailed, and effective in addressing the research objectives?	Research Methodology.	
	RC5	Are the results and findings clearly discussed?	Results and Findings	
	RC6	Is the experimental environment in which the research is conducted explicitly described, providing a framework that facilitates replicating the conditions under which the study was carried out?	Experimental Environment of the Research	
	RC7	Is the established sample representative and sufficient to meet the research objectives?	Established Sample	
	RC8	Are the steps taken for data processing described in a clear and replicable manner?	Data Processing	
	RC9	Is the data analysis presented in a clear and coherent manner?	Data Analysis	
	Relevance	RC10	Does the article highlight the study's implications in the real-world context (industry and/or academia) and its relevance to the academic and professional community?	Implications of the Study in the Real-World Context
		RC11	Does the study present a clear proposal on future work, challenges, trends, and research gaps?	Proposal, Future Work, Trends, and Gaps
Credibility	RC12	Does the study clearly describe the discussion through the analysis of the research process conducted and the results?	Analysis of the Investigation Process	
	RC13	Are the results presented clearly in the study?	Clarity of the Results	